

CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND PROFITABILITY OF LISTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

¹Bello, Adeleke H., ²Adewoye, Jonathan O., ³Akosile, Iyiola A. and ⁴Okewole, Jacob A.

^{1,2,3}Department of Accounting and Finance, Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Ikeje, Osun State, Nigeria

⁴The Oke Ogun Polytechnic, Saki, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Optimal capital structure mix that will enhance profitability remains a controversial issue among listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study investigated the effect of capital structure mix on profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design using panel data extracted from the 26 selected listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria out of 52 listed manufacturing companies in NEG as at 31st December, 2023. Purposive and stratified sampling techniques were used to select 26 listed manufacturing companies. Panel data were extracted from the annual reports of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Inferential statistics were used to analyze data. The study found that: Debt Equity Ratio, Capital Gearing Ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio and Firm Size have insignificant impact on Return on Asset with t-statistic of 1.21 (pv= 0.22), 0.07 (pv =0.942), 1.45(pv=0.148) and 1.14(pv=0.255) respectively. The debt-asset ratio has a significant influence on Return on Asset with t= -3.82 (pv=0.000). Wald statistic value of 20, 34 (pv =0.0011) showed that all capital structure variables have a joint effect on ROA. DER has a significant influence on ROE with t-statistic = -3.61 (p=0.000), whereas DAR, CGR, ICR and FS have an insignificant impact on ROE with t-statistic = 1.45 (pv=0.148); -0.06 (pv=0.953); 0, 74 (pv=0.461) and -1.41 (pv=0.158) respectively. The Wald test with a value of 15.97 (pv =0.000069) showed that all capital structure variables have a statistically significant influence on ROE. The study concluded that the capital structure mix has a significant influence on the profitability of the selected listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that cited manufacturing companies should optimally use the capital structure to improve their profitability.

Keywords: Capital Structure Mix, Return on Asset, Return on Equity.

Introduction

Manufacturing sector is a crucial component of the Nigerian economy, contributing significantly to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing employment opportunities for millions of Nigerians. However, the sector has faced numerous challenges in the recent years, the including inadequate funding, inefficient management, and intense competition. One of the critical factors that can affect manufacturing firms' performance is their capital structure. Capital structure refers to a firm's mix of debt and equity financing to fund its operations and investments. A firm's capital structure can influence its COC risk profile, and ultimately, its financial performance.

Investors and potential investors will be obliged to invest their hard-earned savings in a company that promises to make a return that will change their wealth position at a certain point in time. However, as sound as this

objective is, it will be elusive if the hard-earned resources are not optimally utilized. The essence of capital structure decisions is to ensure the right combination of financing resources that will yield maximum return without necessarily hampering the interest of stakeholders (Fatoki et al., 2021). A company's capital expenditure is a subject of available funds. Firms need huge investment outlays to meet their investment objectives. The choice of funding sources is subject to multivariate factors. Internal sources, such as retained earnings, and external sources, such as loans in the form of debt or issued shares in the capital market, can be used as financing sources (Hayati & Muchtar, 2022). In view of the above, managers carefully pay attention to selecting a capital mix of debt and equity to achieve resource optimization, which will improve firm value. Theoretical and empirical research have existed in capital structure since the path-breaking work by Miller and Modigliani published in 1958 (Mahmoud, 2017). Existing pieces of literature on capital structure mix are primarily focused on developed nations rather than developing nations, and this remains a gaps in the extant literature (Mahmoud, 2017).

According to capital structure theories, the most important decision a corporation can make is the the composition of debt and equity used to enhance the company's value and lower the cost of capital (Agliardi & Nicos, 2013). Moreover, capital structure combination is considered as a critical and strategic decision that has historically been observed to be puzzling (Kumar, *et al.* 2017). Therefore, capital structure decisions dynamically affect firm performance and are an essential and inextricable part of the stockholders' wealth maximization goal.

Statement of the problem

The choice of capital structure mix has a significant effect on the profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Manufacturing firms face the problem of capital structure decision challenges in terms of the ability to fulfill both long-term and short-term financial obligations, which reduces firms' profitability (Ogunade, 2019). There is no consensus regarding the impact of the capital structure mix on profitability. Some pieces of literature established a positive insignificant association between capital structure and ROA and ROE while some have negative and significant effects. Owolabi et al., (2021) affirmed that equity had a negative but insignificant influence on profitability. Suleiman et al., (2022) affirmed that share capital has a positive but insignificant influence on the ROA of listed money deposit banks in Nigeria. Basseyy et al., (2016) used retained earnings as an independent variable. Onoja and Ovayioza (2015) affirmed that long-term debt has a positive insignificant variant with the firm's financial performance proxy as ROA and ROE. The ratio of short-term debt to total assets significantly affects firm value. Olaoye and Adesina (2022) used the Debt-Equity ratio, short-term debt, and long-term debt to total assets as independent variables. Return on Equity and Return on Assets were used as a proxy for financial performance. Olaoye and Adesina (2022) established that DER has an insignificant negative effect on ROA, while it has a significant negative influence on ROE. Kim *et al.*, (2023) used current and debt-equity ratios as proxies for the capital structure of ICT companies in Kenya. The study posited that current and debt-to-equity ratios have negatively impact companies' financial performance. Debt financing decreases the entity's profit (Narasaih, 2020). The debt decrease the financial performance of manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria. The short-term and long-term debt ratios have a negative influence on ROA and ROE. Inconsistencies in the outcomes of the extant literatures prompt the investigation on the effect of capital structure mix on the profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Objective of the study

The study investigated the impact of capital structure mix on the profitability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The following are the study's specific objectives:

- i. Assess the impact of capital structure on the ROA of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

ii. Examine the impact of capital structure on the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant impact of capital structure mix on the ROA of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ho2: The capital structure mix has no significant impact on the ROE of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Capital Structure Mix

The capital structure mix has been described as the company's chosen combination of debt, preferred stock, and common equity to generate cash (Ajayi et al., 2021). Ajibola et al., (2018) refer to capital structure as a structure that reflects each component of finance, from equity to debt that a company uses to finance its operations. Many firms face the problem of choosing between equity and debt, especially in funding their long-term investment opportunities. Capital structure refers to the financing methods used by a company to fund its operations and growth, which includes both equity and debt. This approach aims to optimize returns for stakeholders while managing risk levels to maximize the firm's value (Dada & Ghazali, 2016). Capital structure is an important aspect of corporate finance that plays an essential role in determining a company's financial health and profitability.

Profitability

According to the existing literatures, many indicators have been used to measure profitability, such as: return on assets, return on equity, gross margin, net profit and asset use. According to the pecking order theory, firms with high profitability will borrow less. In addition, managers can manipulate liquid assets in favour of shareholders against the interest of debt holders, thereby increasing the agency costs of debt (Mahmood, 2017). Most of the existing studies adopted profitability ratios calculated from firms' annual reports, such as: Return on Asset and Return on Equity (Ajibola et al., 2018; Ebaid, 2009; Saedi & Mahmood, 2009; Abor, 2005).

Return on Equity

Return on Equity (ROE) is a measure of a company's net income divided by its shareholders' equity. ROE is a measure of a corporation's profitability and how efficiently it generates those profits. The higher the ROE, the better a company converts its equity financing into profits (Onaolapo & Kajola, 2010).

Return on Assets

Return on Asset (ROA) is a measure commonly used to measure the profitability of a firm's operations. Return on assets measures the profitability of the firm in terms of its assets. It also indicates the overall financial health of a firm. ROA is a good measure for evaluating a firm's financial performance. In addition, it is a measure used by many other researchers when evaluating the effect of capital structure on a firm's performance. Therefore, it will be used in our regression model as a measure of financial performance. ROA is a ratio that shows the results of the total assets used in the company (Kasmir, 2014). ROA is a profitability ratio used to measure the company's effectiveness in generating profits by utilizing its total assets. Syardiana (2015) described ROA as a ratio that demonstrates a company's ability to generate net income using total assets. The greater the ROA results, the better the company's performance.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the pecking order theory developed by Stewart Myers and Nicolas Majluf (1984) and is based on the concept that firms prioritize sources of financing their investment. According to theorists, asymmetric information exists between managers and investors. Thus, investors would want higher returns to compensate for the risk they are taking and less information at their disposal (Olayemi & Fakayode, 2021). The

theory proposes that a firm has three sources of finance: internal finances, debt, and the issue of new shares. Based on the pecking order theory, corporations rank their preferred source of funding with internal sources being the most preferred. Therefore, in circumstances where internal sources are inadequate, a firm will go for debt financing with issuing new shares being the last option, which is least preferred (Ngatia *et al.*, 2022). The theory is relevant to financial restructuring as it guides manufacturing firms on the priority that can be followed about financing projects for improved financial performance, which is explained by the findings of the study that an increase in the use of debt capital reduces financial performance (Ngatia *et al.*, 2022).

Therefore, the conclusion drawn based on asymmetric information is that firms have a hierarchy of financing preferences; firms initially rely on internal funds or turn to debt and later issue equity to cover the remaining capital if it is needed. Internal financing is the cheapest source of financing in contrast to external sources such as debt or equity. Of the two external sources, firms prefer debt financing because of the lower cost of obtaining as opposed to equity financing (Adeoye & Araoye, 2021). The theory has no well-defined target debt/equity ratio and each firm's observed debt ratio simply reflects the firm's cumulative requirement for external finance over an extended period (Adeoye & Araoye, 2021). According to the pecking order model, firms will first use internal funds (retained earnings) before issuing debt and will only issue equity under duress or when the investment requirement so far exceeds debt capacity that it would lead to excessive leverage (Adeoye&Araoye, 2021).

Empirical Review

Rupeli (2019) examined the relationship between capital structure and profitability of manufacturing companies in the Indian manufacturing sector by employing firm-level data (a sample of 54 FDI companies from the S & P BSE 500 index) for a period of 9 years (2010-2018) using a multiple regression model for data analysis. The study revealed that the sampled companies had low debt levels in their capital structure, and short-term debt funds are an important mode of financing adopted by the sample FDI companies. Liquidity has a positive and significant impact on ROTI but a significant and negative impact on ROE. Tangibility has a significant negative impact on ROE, and growth, size, and age have no significant impact on profitability. The study concluded that capital structure does not significantly impact profitability.

Narasaiah (2020) investigated the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of listed firms in the Bombay Stock Exchange by examining 100 manufacturing companies in India between 2014 and 2019. Econometric models were applied for panel data analysis and used pooled OLS estimation, fixed effect, and random effect methodology along with the Hausman test and Ramsey RESET four accounting measures were used to measure performance ROA, ROE, EPS, and Tobin's Q. Pearson's correlation and regression techniques were employed, revealing a negative relationship among SIDR, LTDR, and ROE. Furthermore, the result revealed a significant negative relationship among the capital structure variables as LTDR and TDR with the financial performance measured by ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q.

Arikekpar (2020) used a fixed effect regression model to evaluate the impact of capital structure on a firm's performance for 5 years (2014-2018). The study used ROA, ROE, and EPS as proxies for a firm's performance and equity ratio to debt ratio as indicators of capital structures. The study revealed that capital structure has a significant positive effect on the financial performance of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. Variables such as: asset turnover, capital gearing, EBITDA and interest coverage were not used in the study. The study did not use control variables.

Olaoye and Adesina (2022) studied the effect of capital mix on the financial performance of 10 manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) for 12 years period, spanning 2009 to 2020. Secondary data were extracted from the audited accounts and reports of the selected firms. This study employed

descriptive and inferential statistical analyses for data estimation. The results of this work revealed that debt about equity (DER) has an insignificant adverse effect on the selected firms’ return on assets (ROA). Contrarily, DER has a direct significant effect on ROE and a direct insignificant effect on the NPM of the sampled manufacturing companies. Total debt to total assets (TDTA) has a positive but insignificant effect on all financial performance indicators. The study also found that STDA and LDTA have negative effects on all the dependent variables.

Anozie et al. (2023) investigated the impact of capital structure on Nigerian oil and gas companies’ financial performance. Using an ex-post facto research methodology, the short-term debt to total assets, long assets, long-term debt to total assets were investigated as proxies for capital structure and financial performance, respectively. Based on the data’s availability at the time of the inquiry, an easy sampling strategy was used to gather secondary data. These data were compiled from the annual financial reports of five Nigerian oil and gas companies and covered the years 2011 through 2020. Descriptive statistics and panel regression analysis were performed to analyze the data. The analysis findings show that while long-term debt-to-total assets has a significant negative influence on return on assets, short-term debt-to-total assets and total debt-to-total equity have insignificant positive impact on the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Gaps in Literature

Previous studies have reported conflicting findings regarding the effect of capital structure and firm performance, with some suggesting a positive relationship and others finding a negative relationship (Olokoyo, 2011; Abor, 2005). Existing literature has used returns on equity and assets as proxy to measure financial performance. However, the inconsistencies in the outcomes of the extant literature on the impact of capital structure components of ROA and ROE motivated this study. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of capital structure on the profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria using ROA and ROE as measures of profitability.

Methodology

The study adopted an *ex post facto* research design. The design was used in this research work to analyze secondary data because no experiment was involved, but it was designed to test an event that had already occurred. The population for the study comprised all 52 manufacturing companies that are listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NEG)) as of 31st December 2023 (NSE, 2023). The sample size of 26 companies was sampled from manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group. Purposive and stratified sampling techniques were adopted to draw the samples from consumer goods, health care, industrial goods, conglomerates, and agriculture between 2014 and 2023. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses.

Model Specification and Interpretation of the Results

This study adopted the model applied by Ajibola et al. (2018) with minor modifications to accommodate more variables to suit the study’s objective. A firm’s size may influence its performance; a larger firm may have more capacity and capabilities. Firm size is a major factor in determining firm profitability. Firm size is measured by total assets, total revenue, market capitalization, and total sales. Therefore, this study controls the differences in a firm’s operating environment by including the size. Size is measured by the log of the firm’s total assets and was included in the model to control for the effects of capital structure on the dependent variable, i.e. financial performance.

Profitability is $f(\text{Capital Structure})$

This was operationalized as follows:

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DER} + \beta_2\text{DAR} + \beta_3\text{CGR} + \beta_4\text{ICR} + \beta_5\text{FS} + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots \text{i}$$

$$\text{ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{DER} + \beta_2\text{DAR} + \beta_3\text{CGR} + \beta_4\text{ICR} + \beta_5\text{FS} + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots \text{ii}$$

Where:

Financial performance = (ROA and ROE)

Capital Structure = (DER, DAR, CGR, ICR, and FS)

Interpretation of the models

Dependent Variables

ROA, ROE, proxy for selected firms' profitability

B0 = Intercept or constant variable

B1, B2, B3....., B5 = coefficient of the independent variables considered in the study U_{it} = disturbance or un-estimated error term

DER: Debt-Equity Ratio

DAR: Debt: Assets Ratio

Capital Gearing Ratio (CGR)

ICR- Interest Coverage Ratio

FS, Firm Size

Variable Measurement and Justification

S/N Variables	Measurement	Sources
1 Profitability		
i. Return on the Asset	Return on Asset = Profit after Interest and Taxes/Total Assets X 100	Dang et al. (2019), Narasiah (2020), Arikekpar (2020), Mahfuzah and Raj (2021), Tatoki et al. (2021), Olaoye and Adesina (2022)
ii. Return on Equity	Return on Capital Employed = Profit after Interest and Taxes/Capital Employed X100	Narasaiah (2020), Arikekpar (2020), Fatoki et al. (2021). Olaoye&Adesina (2022).
2 Capital Structure		
i. Debt/Equity Ratio	Debt/Equity Ratio = Long-term debts/shareholders' funds or net worth	Rupelis (2019), Narasaiah (2020), Arikekpar (2020), Ajayi et al. (2021), Fatoki et al. (2021),Opoku-Asante et al. (2022), Olaoye&Adesina (2022)
ii. Debt/Assets Ratio	Debt/Average Ratio = Debt/Total Assets	Rupelis (2019) and Narasaiah (2020)

- iii. Capital Gearing Ratio = net worth Okpe et al. (2018), Usman or equity capital/fixed interest- (2019), and Yusuf (2022) bearing securities
- iv Interest coverage ratio Interest Coverage Ratio = Net Afolabi et al. (2019), Profit Before Interest and Taxes/ Anifowose et al. (2020), Obia Fixed interest rates (2020), and Osamor et al. (2023).

4 Control Variable

- i. Firm Size Measured as the total assets log Rupelis (2019), Ajayi et al. (2021)

Source: Researchers’ Computation, 2025.

Results

Test of Hypothesis One

Capital structure has no significant effect on the Return on Asset of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Model One				
Random				
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t-test	Prob.
Constant	-0.018	0.08487	-0.22	0.829
DER	0.002	0.00167	1.21	0.227
DAR	-0.055	0.01435	-3.82	0.000
CGR	0.0589	0.0814	0.07	0.942
ICR	0.0001	0.00007	1.45	0.148
FS	0.1281	0.01127	1.14	0.255
Adj. R ² ; Prob. (F-Stat)	0.0869 (0.0000)			
Diagnostics Test	Statistics		Prob.	
Wald-Stat	20.34		0.0011	
Hausman Test	0.89		0.912	
Breusch-Pagan LM test	1.000		0,000	
Heteroskedasticity Test	119.19		0.000	

Source: Researcher`s computation (2025)

The table above shows the results of the regression analysis of the effect of capital structure on ROA in listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The results show that the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size have a positive relationship with the ROA of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, while the debt asset ratio is negatively related. In addition, there is evidence that the debt asset ratio has a significant relationship with the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DAR = 0.055, t-test= -3.82, p< 0.05, with p-value less than 0.05). The inference from this is that the debt–asset ratio is a significant factor influencing changes in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

On the contrary, the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size do not have a significant relationship with the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DER = 0.002, t-test = 1.21, $p > 0.05$, CGR = 0.005, t-test = 0.07, $p > 0.05$, ICR = 0.0001, t-test = 1.45, $p > 0.05$, FS = 0.0128, t-test = 1.14, $p > 0.05$). This means that the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size are not significant factors that influence changes in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. For the magnitude of the estimated parameters, using the coefficients of the regression analysis, a unit increase in the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size will lead to a 0.2%, 0.5%, 0%, and 1.2% increase in the return on assets, respectively, whereas a 1% decrease in the debt asset ratio will lead to a 0.5% increase in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

F-statistics was employed to determine the overall significance of the independent variables on the dependent variable and to ascertain whether all the coefficients of the independent variables determined are not zero (0). From Table 4.2.1, model 1 gives a p-value of F- statistics equal to 0.0000, and it is significant at 5%. This confirms that the explanatory variables (DER, DAR, CGR, ICR, and FS) are linearly related to the ROA. The Adjusted R² measures the proportion of changes in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria as a result of changes in debt equity ratio, debt asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firms' size, accounting for approximately 8% variation in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Other factors not captured in the model explained the remaining 92% of the changes in the ROA of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The Wald-Test of 15.97 is statistically significant with $p < 0.05$. At the level of significance 0.05. The Wald-Test recorded 15.97, whereas the probability of the Wald-Test was 0.00069, which is less than the 0.05 adopted level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis that capital structures have no significant impact on the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis that capital structures have a significant impact on the ROE of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Capital structure has no significant effect on the return on equity of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

Model Two				
Random-effects model				
Variable	Coeff.	SE	t-test	Prob.
Constant	0.9318	0.5541	1.68	0.093
DER	-0.0395	0,0109	-3.61	0.000
DAR	0.1357	0.0938	1.45	0.148
CGR	0.0031	0.0005	-0.06	0.953
ICR	0.0004	.00005	0.74	0.461
FS	-0.1038	0.0736	-1.41	0.158
Adj. R ² ; Prob. (F-Stat)	0.0733 (0.0000)			
Diagnostics Test				Prob.
Wald-Stat	15.97		0.00069	
Hausman Test	-19.85		0.0695	
Breusch-Pagan LM test	1.000		0.0000	
Heteroskedasticity Test	193.48		0.0000	

Source: Researcher`s computation (2025)

The regression analysis results show that the debt asset ratio and interest cover ratio have a positive relationship with the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, while the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, and firm size have a negative relationship. In addition, only the debt equity ratio has a significant relationship with the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DER = 0.000, t-test= -3.61, $p < 0.5$). This implies that the debt–equity ratio is a significant factor influencing changes in the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

On the contrary, the debt asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size do not have a significant relationship with the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria (DAR = 0.1357, t-test = 1.45, $p > 0.05$, CGR = 0.0003, t-test= -0.06, ICR=0.0004, t-test = 0.74, $p > 0.05$, FS=-0.104, t-test = 1.41). This means that the debt asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size are not significant factors that influence changes in the return on equity of listed manufacturing industries in Nigeria.

Concerning the magnitude of the estimated parameters for the coefficients of the regression analysis, a unit increase in the debt-to-asset ratio and the interest-to-cover ratio will lead to 13.57% and 0.4% increases in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, respectively. While a unit increase in the debt–equity ratio, the capital gearing ratio, and firm size would result in 3.95%, 0.03%, and 10.38% decreases in the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, respectively. This implies that while the debt asset ratio and interest cover ratio have a direct relationship with the return on assets, the debt equity ratio, capital gearing ratio, and firm size have an inverse relationship.

The F-statistic was employed to determine the total significance of the capital structure and firm value (independent variables) on the return on equity (dependent variable) and to confirm that all the estimated coefficients of the independent variables are not zero (0). Model 2, as shown in Table above, has a probability (F-stat) of 0.000, which is lower than the 5% level of significance. This affirms that the independent variables (DER, DAR, CGR, ICR, and FS) are linearly related to the ROE. The Adjusted R^2 which measure the proportion of changes in the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria as a result of changes in debt equity ratio, debt asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, interest cover ratio, and firm size, explains about 7.33% of the changes in the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, while 92.67% accounted for other factors explaining changes in the return on capital of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, which were not captured in the model. This implies that capital structure accounts for very small changes in the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Decision Rule

The Wald-Test of 15.97 is statistically significant with $p < 0.05$. At the level of significance 0.05. The Wald-Test recorded 15.97, whereas the probability of the Wald-Test was 0.00069, which is less than the 0.05 adopted level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis that capital structures have no significant impact on the return on equity of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis that capital structures have a significant impact on the ROE of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria was accepted.

Discussion of the Findings

This study examined the impact of capital structure components such as debt-equity ratio, debt-asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, and interest coverage, regressed against the ROA. Based on the empirical findings, the study affirmed that capital structure significantly influences return on assets. This is in line with the studies of Ngatia et al. (2022), Olaoye et al. (2020), and Arikekpar (2020). The combination of various components of capital structures significantly influenced the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. However, Fatoki et al. (2021), Narasaiah (2020), Olayemi and Fakayode (2021), Olaoye and Adesina (2022),

andAnozie et al. (2023) held contrary empirical findings to the study. The study affirmed that the capital structure components jointly have significant influence on the financial performance of the selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The effect of capital structure components such as debt-equity ratio, debt-asset ratio, capital gearing ratio, and interest coverage, was regressed against the return on equity. Based on the empirical findings, the study affirmed that capital structures significantly influence return on equity. This is in line with the studies of Arikekpar (2020), Ajayi et al. (2021), Olaoye and Adeshina (2022), and Anozie et al. (2023). Contrarily, the studies of Ngatia et al. (2022), Opoku-Asante et al. (2022), and Olayemi and Fatoki(2021) affirmed a negative significant influence on ROE. They affirmed that capital structure components have no influence on ROE. However, the study affirmed that capital structures have a significant effect on profitability.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Capital structure components such as debt-equity ratio, debt- asset ratio, capital gearing, and interest coverage, were regressed again using various financial performance measures, such as RoA and RoE. Capital structure components positively influence ROA and ROE. The effective combination of various capital structure mixes improved the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies. Listed manufacturing firms maximized their equity and asset returns.

Therefore, the study recommends the following based on the empirical findings of the study:

- i. Manufacturing companies should optimally use the capital structure mix to improve their ROA and subsequently improve their overall performance.
- ii. Shareholders' wealth can be improved and maximized through the effective and efficient utilization of capital structure mix. Manufacturing firms should consider the effective dilution of equity and proportion of debts to maximize the return on equity.

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